

Consumer willingness to pay for plant-based foods produced using microbial applications to replace synthetic chemical inputs

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Material A: Frequency tables of respondents' willingness-to-pay (WTP) by gender, age and level of education

S1 Table. Frequency tables of respondents' WTP by gender (percentage of female (F) and male (M) respondents)

WTP	WTP_20% ^a			WTP_50% ^a			WTP_80% ^a			WTP_100% ^a		
	F	M	All	F	M	All	F	M	All	F	M	All
0	11	18	13	6	9	7	4	8	5	1	5	3
1-10 euro cents	26	29	27	18	23	19	13	15	14	11	11	11
11-20 euro cents	32	23	29	33	29	32	18	23	20	12	14	13
21-50 euro cents	19	18	19	27	22	25	36	25	32	22	29	25
>50 euro cents	12	13	13	16	18	16	28	29	29	53	41	49
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

^a WTP_20%, WTP_50%, WTP_80% and WTP_100% refer to respondents' WTP a premium for 1 kg of food product (i.e. consumer potato/wheat bread/tomato sauce) that is produced with a 20%, 50%, 80% and 100% less synthetical chemical use in primary production by replacement with microbial applications, respectively.

11 **S2 Table.** Frequency tables of respondents' WTP by age

WTP	Younger than 37 years		Older than 37 years		Overall (all age group)	
WTP_20%^a	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
0	20	14	9	9	29	12
1-10 euro cents	39	28	26	27	65	27
11-20 euro cents	42	30	27	28	69	29
21-50 euro cents	25	18	21	21	46	19
>50 euro cents	15	11	15	15	30	13
Total	141	100	98	100	239	100
WTP_50%^a						
0	11	8	6	6	17	7
1-10 euro cents	30	21	16	17	46	19
11-20 euro cents	40	29	33	34	73	31
21-50 euro cents	38	27	23	24	61	26
>50 euro cents	21	15	18	19	39	17
Total	140	100	96	100	236	100
WTP_80%^a						
0	7	5	6	6	13	5
1-10 euro cents	24	17	11	11	35	15
11-20 euro cents	28	20	15	15	43	18
21-50 euro cents	43	31	35	36	78	33
>50 euro cents	38	27	30	31	68	29
Total	140	100	97	100	237	100
WTP_100%^a						
0	4	3	5	5	9	4
1-10 euro cents	14	10	11	11	25	11
11-20 euro cents	20	14	10	10	30	13
21-50 euro cents	36	26	25	26	61	26
>50 euro cents	67	48	46	47	113	47
Total	141	100	97	100	238	100

12 ^a *WTP_20%*, *WTP_50%*, *WTP_80%* and *WTP_100%* refer to respondents' WTP a premium for 1 kg of food product
13 (i.e. consumer potato/wheat bread/tomato sauce) that is produced with a 20%, 50%, 80% and 100% less synthetic
14 chemical use in primary production by replacement with microbial applications, respectively.

15 **S3 Table.** Frequency tables of respondents' WTP by level of education (percentage of respondents without and
 16 with higher education)

WTP	WTP_20% ^a			WTP_50% ^a			WTP_80% ^a			WTP_100% ^a		
	Without	With	All	Without	With	All	Without	With	All	Without	With	All
0	16	13	13	9	7	8	7	6	6	4	3	4
1-10 euro cents	18	29	27	16	20	19	9	15	14	9	12	11
11-20 euro cents	36	27	28	27	32	31	16	19	18	9	14	13
21-50 euro cents	16	19	19	31	24	25	31	33	33	18	27	25
>50 euro cents	16	13	13	18	17	17	38	26	29	60	45	47
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

17 ^a WTP_20%, WTP_50%, WTP_80% and WTP_100% refer to respondents' WTP a premium for 1 kg of food product
 18 (i.e. consumer potato/wheat bread/tomato sauce) that is produced with a 20%, 50%, 80% and 100% less synthetical
 19 chemical use in primary production by replacement with microbial applications, respectively.

20 **Supplementary Material B:** Estimation results of the full latent variable model

21 **S4 Table.** Estimation results of the latent variable model by including all the eleven indicators in the measurement
 22 model ^a

	Promotion oriented		Prevention oriented	
	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Coefficient	Std. Err.
Structural model				
Household size	0.15*	0.08	-0.16*	0.09
Age	0.15**	0.07		
Higher education			-0.15**	0.07
Gender	-0.11	0.08	0.13	0.08
Residence	0.13*	0.08	-0.18**	0.08
Income	-0.12*	0.07		
Expenditure			0.20***	0.07
Consumption frequency			0.14*	0.08
Product type	0.18***	0.08	0.18*	0.09
Purchasing place	0.10	0.07		
Potato			0.15*	0.08
Germany	-0.21***	0.09	0.13	0.10
Netherlands	-0.13*	0.08	0.21**	0.09
Other country			0.11	0.08
Environmental concern			-0.23***	0.07
Health concern	0.30***	0.07		
Attitude towards microbial application	0.17**	0.08	-0.17**	0.09
Measurement model				
FCM1	0.45***	0.07		
FCM2	0.71***	0.05		
FCM3	0.06	0.09		
FCM4	0.51***	0.07		
FCM5	0.84***	0.04		
FCM6	0.43***	0.07		
FCM7			0.30***	0.08
FCM8			0.83***	0.05
FCM9			-0.02	0.09
FCM10			0.07	0.09
FCM11			0.74***	0.06
Goodness-of-fit measures				
RMSEA	0.07 ^b			
CFI	0.65 ^b			
SRMR	0.07^b			
Error term covariances				
Promotion oriented	0.57	0.07		
Prevention oriented	-0.70***	0.09	0.73	0.07

23 ^a N = 158. ^b The cut-off values for acceptance of the goodness-of-fit of the specified model are ≤ 0.06 for RMSEA,
 24 >=0.95 for CFI and ≤0.08 for SRMR. The SRMR measure of model goodness-of-fit indicates that the indicators
 25 used in the latent variables' construction are acceptable in defining the constructs.

26 Likelihood ratio test of model vs. saturated: Chi²(261) = 464***.

27 ***, **, *Significant at 1%, 5% and 10% critical levels, respectively.

28 **Supplementary Material C: Ordered logistic estimation results of the WTP regression model**

29 The maximum likelihood estimation results and the respective marginal effects of the ordered logistic WTP model
30 are presented in S5 and S6 Tables. The likelihood ratio test shows that the included explanatory variables are
31 jointly significant in explaining the variation in predicted probabilities of WTP at 1% critical level (S5 Table).
32 Both the promotion- and prevention-oriented FCM latent variables do not have a significant association with the
33 predicted probabilities of the WTP categories, except for the case of *WTP_80%* where the promotion-oriented
34 construct is statistically significant (S5 Table). The only significant explanatory variables that affect the predicted
35 probabilities of WTP are environmental and health concerns, and the dummy variables used to codify potato,
36 Germany, Finland and other countries. The average predicted probability of the WTP categories for a 20%
37 reduction in chemical use is lower by about 3% and 5% for a one unit increase in environmental and health concern,
38 respectively (S6 Table). This implies that highly (environmental and health) concerned consumers are less likely
39 to pay premiums for food products that are produced with microbial applications.

S5 Table. Maximum likelihood estimation results of the ordered logistic WTP model

Variables	WTP_20%		WTP_50%		WTP_80%		WTP_100%	
	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE
Promotion oriented FCM	0.59	0.50	0.51	0.54	1.05*	0.60	0.07	0.64
Prevention oriented FCM	0.25	0.26	0.15	0.28	0.43	0.32	-0.24	0.30
Attitude	-0.06	0.22	0.15	0.20	0.33*	0.19	0.35*	0.19
Microbial knowledge	0.09	0.14	0.09	0.13	0.06	0.13	-0.08	0.14
Microbial health risk	-0.15	0.25	-0.31	0.25	-0.20	0.23	-0.28	0.22
Environmental concern	0.35*	0.21	0.55**	0.20	0.29*	0.17	0.40**	0.17
Health concern	0.49**	0.20	0.39*	0.21	0.47**	0.21	0.68***	0.24
Household size	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.07	0.12	0.01	0.12
Age	-0.01	0.01	-0.02*	0.01	-0.02*	0.01	-0.02**	0.01
Higher education	0.22	0.33	0.23	0.30	-0.10	0.32	-0.47	0.41
Gender	0.11	0.30	0.25	0.31	0.08	0.33	-0.20	0.31
Residence	-0.15	0.29	-0.18	0.28	-0.07	0.30	-0.10	0.33
Income	0.02	0.08	0.05	0.08	0.04	0.08	0.09	0.08
Expenditure	0.04	0.15	0.03	0.17	-0.04	0.16	0.05	0.17
Consumption frequency	0.25	0.19	0.25	0.17	0.32**	0.17	0.32**	0.15
Product type	-0.36	0.35	-0.07	0.34	-0.39	0.38	-0.04	0.37
Purchasing place	0.05	0.21	0.08	0.16	0.12	0.17	0.17	0.18
Potato	1.76**	0.73	1.17*	0.65	1.11*	0.64	0.63	0.61
Tomato	-0.06	0.41	-0.02	0.40	0.35	0.40	0.04	0.40
Germany	1.76***	0.55	1.59***	0.54	1.40***	0.53	0.88*	0.51
Netherlands	-0.18	0.45	0.13	0.51	0.02	0.52	0.04	0.53
Finland	1.63***	0.60	1.80*	1.00	0.69	0.81	0.65	0.77
Other country	-1.11**	0.55	-0.91*	0.51	-1.10**	0.54	-0.75	0.55
Threshold 1	3.19	1.62	2.97	1.69	2.91	1.49	2.29	1.70
Threshold 2	4.98	1.61	4.88	1.72	4.73	1.47	4.05	1.68
Threshold 3	6.50	1.63	6.68	1.75	5.95	1.48	5.08	1.68
Threshold 4	7.95	1.67	8.33	1.77	7.68	1.51	6.59	1.72
<i>Goodness-of-fit</i>								
Observations	213		211		211		213	
Log likelihood	-299.29		-283.12		-279.05		-242.43	
Likelihood ratio test of zero slope coefficients	59.36***		61.47***		59.43***		69.43***	
Pseudo R ²	0.09		0.10		0.09		0.12	

41 Abbreviations: *WTP_20%*, *WTP_50%*, *WTP_80%* and *WTP_100%* refer to respondents' willingness to pay a
42 premium for 1 kg of food product (i.e. consumer potato/wheat bread/tomato sauce) that is produced with a 20%,
43 50%, 80% and 100% less chemical use in farming due to microbial applications, respectively.

44 ***, **, *Significant at 1%, 5% and 10% critical levels, respectively.

45 **S6 Table. Marginal effects of the ordered logistic regression estimation of the WTP model**

Variables	WTP_20%		WTP_50%		WTP_80%		WTP_100%	
	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE
Promotion oriented FCM	-0.056	0.049	-0.026	0.029	-0.039	0.027	-0.002	0.017
Prevention oriented FCM	-0.024	0.026	-0.008	0.015	-0.016	0.014	0.006	0.008
Attitude	0.006	0.020	-0.008	0.011	-0.012	0.008	-0.009	0.007
Microbial knowledge	-0.009	0.013	-0.005	0.006	-0.002	0.005	0.002	0.004
Microbial health risk	0.014	0.024	0.015	0.013	0.007	0.009	0.007	0.006
Environmental concern	-0.033*	0.019	-0.028**	0.012	-0.011*	0.007	-0.010*	0.006
Health concern	-0.047**	0.020	-0.020*	0.012	-0.017**	0.009	-0.018**	0.009
Household size	-0.010	0.010	-0.005	0.005	-0.003	0.005	0.000	0.003
Age	0.000	0.001	0.001*	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000
Higher education	-0.021	0.032	-0.012	0.015	0.004	0.012	0.012	0.012
Gender	-0.010	0.029	-0.013	0.016	-0.003	0.012	0.005	0.009
Residence	0.014	0.028	0.009	0.015	0.002	0.011	0.003	0.009
Income	-0.001	0.008	-0.002	0.004	-0.002	0.003	-0.002	0.002
Expenditure	-0.004	0.014	-0.001	0.008	0.001	0.006	-0.001	0.005
Consumption frequency	-0.023	0.019	-0.013	0.009	-0.012*	0.007	-0.008*	0.005
Product type	0.034	0.034	0.004	0.017	0.015	0.015	0.001	0.010
Purchasing place	-0.005	0.019	-0.004	0.008	-0.004	0.007	-0.004	0.005
Potato	-0.167**	0.071	-0.059*	0.036	-0.041	0.027	-0.016	0.017
Tomato	0.006	0.038	0.001	0.020	-0.013	0.016	-0.001	0.010
Germany	-0.167***	0.054	-0.080***	0.032	-0.052**	0.026	-0.023	0.016
Netherlands	0.017	0.043	-0.007	0.025	-0.001	0.019	-0.001	0.014
Finland	-0.154***	0.059	-0.091*	0.055	-0.026	0.031	-0.017	0.021
Other country	0.105**	0.051	0.046*	0.027	0.041*	0.024	0.020	0.015

46 Abbreviations: WTP_20%, WTP_50%, WTP_80% and WTP_100% refer to respondents' willingness to pay a
47 premium for 1 kg of food product (i.e. consumer potato/wheat bread/tomato sauce) that is produced with a 20%,
48 50%, 80% and 100% less chemical use in farming due to microbial applications, respectively.
49 ***, **, *Significant at 1%, 5% and 10% critical levels, respectively.